

Labeo rosae Rednose labeo

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Phylum: Chordata

Estimated genome size: 1 560 million DNA base pairs (1.56 Gigabases)

Organism size: Up to 41 cms in length

Distribution:

The Rednose labeo is found in the Limpopo River, Incomati River and Pongola River basins in Southern Africa.

Importance:

The Rednose labeo is a freshwater fish endemic to Southern Africa. Preliminary unpublished short DNA sequence data suggest additional taxonomic diversity within this taxon, but comprehensive genomic data are necessary to resolve its phylogenetic relationships and refine its taxonomic diversity. Although the species is currently listed as Least Concern on the IUCN Red List, its population is experiencing a decline due to impacts of human activities. The Rednose labeo is important for subsistence fisheries.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 55.99 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 8.59 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics: Genome length: 1.09 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 98.4%

[Single: 94.5%, Duplicated: 3.9%]

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